

The importance of lexis in linguist between English and Uzbek languages

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Linguistics is a broad sphere and its primary purpose is to study how languages came to their current form and what kinds of distinctive features differentiate them. Any language consists of some words and lexis, and the field that studies them is lexicology. Lexicology is one of the main branches of linguistics, which mainly studies the vocabulary of a language and the formation of vocabulary. Its main unit is the lexicon, which works in close connection with other branches of linguistics. The difference between lexicon and other branches of linguistics is that it consists of a complex system subject to rules. Although the English and Uzbek languages belong to different language families. First of all, let's examine the similarities of the English and Uzbek lexicon through some examples.

Both the English language and the Uzbek language are subject to stylistic rules. In the process of speaking, the speech of the

ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the similarities and differences between the concept of the lexicon and its importance in the English and Uzbek languages, focusing on their lexicological aspect. Our analysis illustrates that there exist several common and different peculiarities of the lexicon in both languages.

speaker depending on the situation and place is called this methodology. Both languages contain five styles.

➤ conversational style

1. artistic style

1. formal style

• scientific method

• journalistic style

For example, *grandmother* is a formal style, and *granny* is colloquial.

Bajarilsin (Let it be done) is a word in official style, *xabar berildi (reported)* is a word in journalistic style.

2. A certain part of the words in the language forms a whole, interconnected by form or meaning. There are four such word forms in both English and Uzbek:

synonyms, antonyms, homonyms, and paronyms.

Synonyms in English:

Synonyms in Uzbek:

Small, little, tiny osmon,

fazo, ko'k, koinot (sky)

Angry, annoyed, irritated yuz,

oraz, chehra, aft (face)

Happy, cheerful, joyful chiroyli,

go'zal, maftunkor

Antonyms in English: **Antonyms**

in Uzbek:

Strong - weak mehnatsevar

ƒdangasa (hardworking-lazy)

Ancient - modern boy -

kambag'al (rich - poor)

Fearful - brave ijobiy -

salbiy (positive - negative)

Homonyms in English: **English:**

Homonyms in Uzbek:

Leave - 1. go away from o't - 1.

Olov (fire)

2. *allow or cause* 2.

o'simlik turi (grass)

3. *to remain.* 3.

o'tmoq (to pass)

Paronyms in English: **Paronyms**

in Uzbek:

Write - right tarif - ta'rif

(tariff - definition)

Whole - hole teri - tire

(skin - dash)

Insight - incite kompaniya-

kampaniya(company,campaign)¹

3. Another similarity between the lexicons of the following two languages is **word formation**. Word formation is the creation of a new word based on the methods, patterns and patterns available in a particular language. In both English and

Uzbek, words are made mainly by two methods: **syntactic(composition)** and **morphological(affixation)**

In the method of **composition**, one independent word is made from the union of two independent words. Let's take the English words *lifestyle* and *blackboard* as examples.

Lifestyle = life + style *blackboard = black + board*

(Noun = noun + noun) *(Noun = adjective + noun)*

As an example of syntactic word formation in Uzbek, let's take the words *kungaboqar (sunflower)* and *ko'zoynak (glasses)*.

Kungaboqar = kun + boq *ko'zoynak = ko'z + oynak*

(Noun = noun + verb) *(Noun = noun + noun)*

Affixation is one of the most common ways of creating a new word in modern English, and is formed by word-forming additions that give a word a new meaning. Affixation includes **prefixes** ("prefix" - "addition added to the front of a word"), **affixes** ("suffix" - "additions of form added to the end of a word") and **infixes** ("infix" - "new word-forming affixes added to the word stem").²

For example, "*greener*" - a new person or a young employee; "*drunkie*" - wine drinker, alcoholic; "*jumper*" - thief. "*no-hoper*" is an unlucky, useless person.

We can show the word formation of the words *odobli (polite)*, *unumdor (productive)*, and *baquvvat (energetic)* in the **Uzbek** language in a syntactic way.

The differences between English and Uzbek lexicology.

¹ Tursunov U. va boshqa, Hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tili, T., 1965;

² <https://uz.m.wikipedia.org>

1. One of the distinguishing aspects of the lexicology of English and Uzbek languages is the division from the point of **view of modernity**.

The modernity of the Uzbek language vocabulary is divided into 3 basic layers:

1. Modern layer - words that do not have the characteristics of oldness and newness. Words related to this layer form the basis of the lexicon of the Uzbek language;
2. The ancient layer - ancient words, although they are words that appear in our speech today.
3. A new layer - words without restrictions on the scope of use. Words whose meaning is understandable to speakers of this language and have a universal character.³

However, in English, there are not this kind of modernity.

2. The next major and significant difference between English and Uzbek lexicology is the **article**, which is considered one of the most important parts of the English language. Articles are used before nouns and are a type of adjective.

There are two types of articles in English – **Definite** and **Indefinite** Articles. "The" is the only Definite Article and the Indefinite Articles are "a" and "an". The article "an" can be used when you wish to talk about an indefinite noun that begins with a vowel sound.

Definite article - the (before a singular or plural noun)

Indefinite article - a (before a singular noun beginning with a consonant sound); an (before a singular noun beginning with a vowel sound). For instance:

Use the article **a** before a consonant sound, and use **an** before a vowel sound: **a** boy, **an** apple; **a** neighbor, **an** apartment

Use the article **the** when a particular noun has already been mentioned previously: *I ate **an** apple yesterday. **The** apple was juicy and delicious.*

Sometimes **an adjective** comes between the article and noun: **an** unhappy boy, **a** red apple; **an** international language, **a** close friend

But there are no such elements in the Uzbek language. Nouns are preceded by a **number** to express count, and an **adjective** is placed before nouns to express a sign.

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³ www.theguardian.com